

PERCEPTIONS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS FOR THE DEMOCRACY CONCEPT: A METAPHORIC STUDY

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Abstract:

Although democracy is generally defined as a form of government based on the sovereignty of the people, it is also a phenomenon that makes itself felt in all areas of life. It is possible for democracy to function in all segments of society with the existence of individuals who adopt democratic knowledge, skills, attitudes and values. A democratic culture of life can be achieved through schools and lessons. At this point, determining the perceptions of students who will be citizens of the future towards the concept of democracy will contribute to the formation of a democratic life culture. The aim of this study is to reveal the perceptions of secondary school students about the concept of democracy through metaphors. The study group of this research consists of 165 5th, 6th, 7th and 8th grade students who are continuing their education at a public school in Hilvan district of Şanlıurfa province in the spring term of 2016-2017 academic year. The participants were asked to fulfil the “Democracy is like because” expressions featured in the survey form. In this study, the obtained data were analyzed by descriptive analysis. In this study, secondary school students developed 53 metaphors for the concept of “democracy”. These metaphors are respectively the metaphors of freedom, equality, justice, life, election, republic, peace, politics, independence, scales, solidarity, country integrity and freedom of thought. When the metaphors were examined for the categories, students developed the most metaphor in the categories of democracy as a symbol of freedom and democracy as a tool of equality.

Keywords: democracy, metaphor, secondary school, student

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1. Introduction

Democracy is an important concept for everyone all over the world. For this reason, one of the most important goals of education systems is to raise individuals with democratic attitudes and skills. Democratic governance and culture of living are possible only by raising individuals with democratic attitudes and skills. For this reason, secondary school students who will become the future citizens and society leaders must understand the concept and culture of democracy.

Various definitions and explanations regarding the concept of democracy are made in the literature. While Aristotle defined democracy as the best political order; Plato sees the bad as a political system (Kuçuradi, 1998). The Turkish Language Association (2020) defines democracy as *“the form of government based on the sovereignty of the people”*. Democracy, which has increased its prevalence more and more since the 20th century, is seen as the most ideal form of government today (İbret, Receptođlu, Karasu Avci and Receptođlu, 2018). Democracy, which includes important concepts such as effective participation, freedom, voting right and equality, is a system that enables individuals to live in the way they deserve in social life (Dahl, 2001). According to Levin (1998), democracy is a lifestyle and culture rather than a political system. Heywood (1999) explains democracy as the powerful rule the weak. Demir (2013) expresses democracy as the ideal lifestyle to be reached. Ural (1999) states that the most prominent feature of democracy is rights and freedoms. In this context, it is seen that the concept of democracy has wide and different meanings.

The functioning of democracy in all segments of society is possible by raising effective citizens who adopt democratic knowledge, skills, attitudes and values. Schools and lessons play an important role in creating a democratic culture of life throughout the society. Continuing the culture of democracy in the family and continuing through the lessons at school ensures that individuals who know the basic principles, values and ways of thinking of democracy and internalize it as a way of life are trained. For this reason, schools have an important responsibility for children to acquire democratic knowledge, skills and values. Dewey states that there is a mutual relationship between education and democracy and that democracy cannot exist without education; he thinks that democracy can be learned by practicing daily life in a school environment that has a culture of democracy and in which the basic characteristics of democracy are adopted (Dewey, 2004; Hotaman, 2009). To ensure a democratic society, a democratic school culture and classroom environment must be created first. To realize this, the perceptions, attitudes and values that teachers themselves have regarding democracy are important in gaining democratic knowledge, skills and values of the individuals they educate.

In order to reveal students' perspectives on democracy, the schemes and images they create in their minds for that concept can be utilized through metaphors. In this context, it will be appropriate to touch on the concept of metaphor in this part of the study. Metaphor is derived from the Greek word *“metapherein”* as a word and is formed by the combination of the words meta (change) and pherein (carry) (Levine, 2005). Saban

(2004) also metaphor; It describes it as the most powerful mental tool that structures, directs and controls ideas about the occurrence and functioning of events. Metaphors help students understand more clearly the difficult concepts and terms more clearly, enabling the abstract concepts to be embodied and visualized in the mind, thereby increasing the motivation of learning by keeping the learned information longer in mind and easier to remember (Arslan & Bayrakçı, 2006). Metaphor: it is also used to redefine facts and encourage reconceptualization of problem situations, as they affect the way situations and events are perceived (Goldstein, 2005).

Since meanings are attached to objects, events and facts through concepts, the concepts that express it must be known in order to understand democracy. It is important to learn and reinforce these concepts in order for these meanings to occur in the minds of children. Teaching is used in learning abstract concepts (Senemođlu, 2009). The fact that the concept of democracy is abstract also makes it difficult to learn and understand. Understanding the place of this concept in life will help develop democracy awareness in individuals. To understand democracy, more concepts about democracy need to be known. The fact that there are few concepts related to democracy in the mental schemes of students creates a narrow understanding of democracy in them; The inclusion of a large number of concepts will provide a broad understanding of democracy. For this reason, the conceptual revealing of the metaphors created by students regarding the concept of democracy will contribute to democracy education.

When the studies on the concept of democracy are examined in the literature, it is generally focused on teacher candidates and teachers (Gürşimşek and Görgeñli; 2004, Emir & Kaya, 2004; Biçer, 2007; Genç & Kalafat, 2007; Kılıç, 2010; Dođanay, 2010; Yüce & Demir, 2011 ; Sadık and Sarı, 2011; Gömlüksiz, Kan and Öner, 2012; Karatekin, Merey, and Kuş, 2013; Yađan Güder and Yıldırım, 2014; Nasırcı and Sadık, 2017; İbret, Recepođlu, Karasu Avcı, Recepođlu, 2018). There are a limited number of studies on secondary school students' perceptions about the concept of democracy (Kaldırım, 2005; Soydaş, 2010; Sadık & Sarı, 2012; Düñdar, 2012; Karatekin & Elvan, 2016). In this context, it is considered important to understand the perceptions of democracy that middle school students produce regarding the concept of "democracy" at a time when it is emphasized that the awareness of democracy should be developed due to the increasing number of wars, internal conflicts and violence in every part of the society. Accordingly, the purpose of this study is to reveal the perceptions of secondary school students about the concept of democracy through metaphors. For this purpose, answers to the following questions were sought:

- 1) What are the perceptions of secondary school students about the concept of democracy?
- 2) What are the explanations of secondary school students for the reason of the metaphors they developed regarding the concept of democracy?
- 3) What are the perceptions of secondary school students according to the reasons and grade level of the metaphors they have developed regarding the concept of democracy?

2. Method

2.1. Model of the Research

Phenomenological research design, one of the qualitative research types, was used in the research. Phenomenology is the technique that reveals the experiences of the participants by determining the common aspects in their views in accordance with the data collected by interviewing with independent participants on a special case (Büyüköztürk, Kılıç Çakmak, Akgün, Karadeniz, & Demirel, 2012). In this study, because the secondary school students were asked to develop metaphors based on their experiences on the concept of democracy, research design was preferred. Lakoff and Johnson (2005) explain the concept of metaphor as the basis of human cognition. The use of metaphors in studies; it is considered to be very useful in describing a situation, event and phenomenon as it exists and presenting a robust, rich picture about the subject, phenomenon, event and situation (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2016). Metaphors are very useful in the patterning of complex information, especially for qualitative researches on facts and concepts (Parsons, Brown & Worley, 2004; Schmitt, 2005).

2.2. Working Group

This research consists of 5th, 6th, 7th, and 8th grade 165 students who continue their education at a public school in the province of Hilvan of Şanlıurfa in the spring semester of the 2016-2017 academic year and agree to participate in the research voluntarily. Accordingly, the sample type of the study has been determined as convenience sampling. Convenience sampling is the type of sampling in which the researcher prefers participants who are easy to reach (Dawson & Trapp, 2001). In this study, Convenience sampling was chosen since one of the researchers served as a teacher in this public school facilitating reaching students.

2.3. Data Collection Tool

In this study, The participants were asked to fulfil the “Democracy is like because” expressions featured in the survey form. The students were given the time (5-10 minutes) they could think enough to complete the sentences. Answers obtained from 165 secondary school students were considered valid. These collected data constituted the main data source of the study. The concept of “because” was included in the study and students were provided to create a rationale for their metaphors. The answers given by the students were kept confidential by the researchers and were not shared with anyone.

2.3. Data Analysis

In this study, the data obtained were analyzed through descriptive analysis. Descriptive analysis is expressed as the situation of interpretation of data obtained using various data collection techniques according to previously determined themes (Özdemir, 2010). The data obtained in the study were analyzed by classifying them according to their similarities and differences.

The analysis of the metaphors developed by the participants was carried out in three stages (Özdemir, 2010):

A. Coding and Extracting Phase

At this stage, the metaphors developed by the students are listed in order. These listed metaphors are sorted by frequency numbers and percentages. Study forms, in which a metaphor was not developed, more than one metaphor was developed and left blank, were excluded from the research. At this stage, the metaphor developed by each student is coded (eg freedom, equality, justice etc.). The categories developed from the metaphors obtained are handled according to the grade level.

B. Sample Metaphor Compilation Stage

After the invalid metaphor forms were removed, these metaphors were reordered and the raw data were revised a second time. A sample metaphor expression was chosen from student compositions representing each metaphor. Thus, a “sample metaphor list” was created with the compilation of student metaphor images, which are assumed to represent him best for each of the 53 metaphors. In cases where a selected metaphor expression is long, only the important dimensions of the metaphor are conveyed, preserving the participants' own words and expression language. Personal information about who produced a metaphor image is given in brackets just behind the metaphor expression in question. The researchers arranged the data they obtained at this stage based on the theoretical framework. Secondary school students participating in the research were first grouped according to their class levels, and then prospective teachers were given codes according to their class levels. For example, 5th grade secondary school student O.Ö.K.5.1., O.Ö.E.5.2., O.Ö.E.5.3, ... O.Ö.K.5.48. It is coded as. The same encodings were carried out within other grade levels.

C. Category Development Phase

At this stage, the metaphors developed by the students were examined by looking at their common features, and how the metaphor of the students was conceptualized. Each metaphor image developed by students was analyzed in terms of the subject of the metaphor, the source of the metaphor, and the relationship between the subject and the source of the metaphor. At this stage of the study, valid metaphors were determined by reading the data. Metaphors were analyzed in terms of the source of the metaphor and the attributes considered to be attributed to the source of the metaphor and common points were identified. Based on this, this study is categorized using the study of Yüce and Demir (2011) entitled “Studying the perceptions of police candidates on the concept of democracy through metaphors”.

2.3.1 Validity and Reliability

In qualitative research, validity is defined as the fact that researchers and readers understand the same thing and make the same inference from the analysis of the data (Creswell, 2013). In this study, validity was tried to be provided by presenting the analysis of the data in detail and the opinions of the secondary school students regarding the findings directly. Reliability in qualitative research is known as reviewing the

obtained data by more than one researcher and making a common decision in conflict situations (Creswell, 2013). The researchers in this study took part in all of the coding, classification and category development stages of the data. The differences in the views were discussed by the researchers and resolved by making a common decision. According to Patton (2014), this is the analyst triangle. Analyst triangulation is when two or more researchers independently analyze a research data and compare the data obtained.

3. Results

In this section, findings are included in the framework of sub-problems. First of all, the metaphors developed by the students were included collectively, then the metaphors were classified according to their sources and finally, they were grouped into the grade levels.

3.1. Findings Related to the First Sub-Problem

In the first sub-problem of the research, "What are the perceptions of secondary school students about the concept of democracy?" The answer to the question was sought. Table 1 presents the metaphors developed by secondary school students regarding the concept of "democracy":

Table 1: Metaphors developed by students regarding the concept of "democracy"

	Metaphor	f	%		Metaphor	f	%
1	Freedom	40	24,2	28	Ataturk	1	0,6
2	Justice	21	12,7	29	Happiness	1	0,6
3	Equality	11	6,6	30	Mind	1	0,6
4	Life	7	4,2	31	Water	1	0,6
5	Election	6	3,6	32	Rain	1	0,6
6	Republic	5	3,0	33	Tree	1	0,6
7	Peace	5	3,0	34	Tree Roots	1	0,6
8	Politics	5	3,0	35	Nation	1	0,6
9	Independence	4	2,4	36	Mother	1	0,6
10	Scales	4	2,4	37	Father	1	0,6
11	Solidarity	3	1,8	38	Sky	1	0,6
12	Brain	3	1,8	39	Order	1	0,6
13	Country Integrity	2	1,2	40	Honesty	1	0,6
14	Freedom of thought	2	1,2	41	Affection	1	0,6
15	Sovereignty	2	1,2	42	Respect	1	0,6
16	State	2	1,2	43	Turkiye	1	0,6
17	Family	2	1,2	44	Guide	1	0,6
18	Marriage	2	1,2	45	Modernization	1	0,6
19	Heart	2	1,2	46	Game Rule	1	0,6
20	Human	2	1,2	47	Unity	1	0,6
21	Life	2	1,2	48	Flower	1	0,6

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22	Need	2	1,2	49	Innovation	1	0,6
23	Education	1	0,6	50	Habit	1	0,6
24	Public	1	0,6	51	A Soldier's Ammunition	1	0,6
25	Advice	1	0,6	52	Baby	1	0,6
26	Difficulty	1	0,6	53	Sycamore	1	0,6
27	Form of Management	1	0,6				
	Total	165	100			165	100

When Table 1 is examined, it is seen that secondary school students develop 53 metaphors for the concept of "democracy". According to this, the most common concept of democracy is "freedom" (f: 40), "equality" (f: 11), "justice" (f: 21), "life" (f: 7), "election" (f: 6).) 'peace" (f: 5), "republic" (f: 5), "independence" (f: 4), "scales" (f: 4) and "solidarity" (f: 3). The development of a large number of different metaphors about the concept of democracy can be explained by the fact that this concept has a comprehensive and broad meaning. In addition, the fact that each student has different experiences and perspectives related to this concept caused them to develop different metaphors.

3.2. Findings Related to the Second Sub-Problem

Table 2: The distribution of students' metaphors about the concept of "democracy" into categories

Democracy Categories	Metaphor	f	%
Democracy as a tool of peace	Peace (5), Happiness (1), Affection (1), Respect (1), Order (1)	9	5,4
Democracy as a valuable and guiding entity	Mother (1), Father (1), Atatürk (1), Honesty (1), Guide (1), Advice (1)	6	3,6
Democracy as a changing factor according to the perspective	-	-	-
Democracy as a tool of equality	Justice (21), Equality (11), Scales (4), Rain (1)	37	22,4
Democracy as a structure of diversity	Selection (6), Family (2), Marriage (2), Turkiye (1), Public (1), Nation (1)	13	7,8
Democracy as a developing and maturing entity	Life (2), Tree (1), Tree Roots (1), Sycamore (1), Flower (1), Baby (1)	7	4,2
Democracy as a factor of power	Sovereignty (2), A Soldier's Ammunition (1), Difficulty (1)	4	2,4
Democracy as a symbol of freedom	Freedom (40), İndependence (4), Freedom of Thought (2) Sky (1)	47	28,4
Democracy as a system factor	Politics (5), Republic (5), Solidarity (3), Brain (3), State (2), Human (2), Country Integrity (2), Unity (1), Form of Government (1), Mind (1)), Modernization (1), Innovation (1)	27	16,3
Democracy as a necessity or requirement	Life (7), Heart (2), Need (2), Water (1), Education (1), Habit (1), Game Rule (1)	15	9,0
Total		165	100

The metaphors developed by the students for the concept of democracy are categorized using the study of Yüce and Demir (2011) titled "Examining the perceptions of the police candidates about the concept of democracy through metaphors". Each metaphor is grouped in the context of thought attributed to the source of the metaphor. The second sub-problem of the research is "What are the explanations of the secondary school students' reasons for the metaphors they have developed regarding the concept of democracy?" The findings regarding the question are given in Table 2.

According to Table 2, the metaphors developed by students are gathered under nine conceptual categories in terms of their common features. Each metaphor is grouped in relation to the thought attributed to the source of the metaphor, in line with the statements made by the students. Accordingly, the students developed the metaphor regarding the categories of "democracy as a symbol of freedom" (f: 47), "democracy as a tool of equality" and "democracy as a system factor" respectively. The category in which students develop the least metaphor is the category of "democracy as a factor of power" (f: 7). However, on the category of "democracy as a changing factor according to the perspective" in the study of Yüce and Demir (2011), it is seen that secondary school students do not develop any metaphors.

Examples of metaphors developed by secondary school students for the concept of democracy are given below, by category:

Category 1: Definitions of Democracy as a tool of Peace

O.Ö.K.6.74. "Democracy is like peace. Because by dealing with someone's fight, they find out who is right and who is wrong. They remain innocent as in our dreams. "

O.Ö.E.7.89 "Democracy is like happiness. Because, thanks to democracy, people can lead their lives in joy and peace, and therefore democracy is like happiness. "

Category 2: Definitions of the Democracy Category as a Valuable and Guiding Entity

O.Ö.K.7.102. "Democracy is like Atatürk. Because when Atatürk established the republic, however, politics came, the people were choosing their own president and president, that is, the root of democracy is Atatürk. "

Category 3: Definitions of the Democracy Category as a tool of Equality

O.Ö.K.7.85 "Democracy is like justice. Thanks to democracy, everyone has the right to vote as they wish. In this way, everyone can vote for the person they want. It is fair. "

O.Ö.K.6.53. "Democracy is like equality. Without democracy, internal confusion in the country means that the wealthy crush the poor, the wealthy people are more defended before the law, and the poor do not care. "

Category 4: Definitions of the Democracy Category as a Structure of Diversity

O.Ö.K.5.20. "Democracy is like Turkey. Because we all agree and make a common decision. "

O.Ö.K.6.65. "Democracy is like marriage. Two people unite, have children and become a family. It is so in the government that it grows and rules the nation. "

O.Ö.E.7.88. "Democracy is like an election. Everyone can use the voting they want with their free will and everyone's vote is confidential. "

Category 5: Definitions of the Democracy Category as a Developing and Maturing Entity

O.Ö.K.8.120. *"Democracy is like a baby. As it grows and develops, it will be effective in making that country a good state in every respect. "*

O.Ö.K.8.147. *"Democracy is like a tree. Because there is a labor in every leaf of every branch of the tree. In democracy, much effort should be made to be equal, to be free, to be independent, to be fair. "*

Category 6: Definitions of the Democracy Category as a Factor of Power

O.Ö.E.8.119. *"Democracy is like sovereignty. Because democracy and sovereignty is power. "*

O.Ö.K.8.135. *"Democracy is like a soldier's ammunition. Because democracy is a sine qua non of a nation. A nation is unthinkable without democracy. "*

Category 7: Definitions of the Democracy Category as a Symbol of Freedom

O.Ö.K.5.11. *"Democracy is like freedom. Every person is free. Every person has their own rights. No person can be happy without freedom. Freedom is one's own life. Nobody can take away people's rights. "*

O.Ö.K.8.151. *"Democracy is like freedom. We are free to do whatever we want and we are very happy. "*

Category 8: Definitions of the Democracy Category as a System Factor

O.Ö.K.5.35. *"Democracy is like the brain of a country. Because the people live freely and make their own decisions. Who chooses to direct himself. "*

O.Ö.K.8.123. *"Democracy is like a republic. Because public statements are valid here. So, it is also a form of management. But the people are self-governing. "*

Category 9: Definitions Regarding Democracy Category as Necessity or Requirement

O.Ö.E.7.91. *"Democracy is like our heart. When our heart does not work, it does not work in our other organs, democracy is like this order. "*

O.Ö.K.8.161. *"Democracy is like life. It gives us the right to life. We determine our own future. "*

3.3 Findings Related to the Third Sub-Problem

The third problem of the research is "What are the perceptions of secondary school students according to the reason and grade level of the metaphors they have developed regarding the concept of democracy?" Table 3 presents the distribution of metaphors developed by secondary school 5th grade students regarding the concept of democracy into categories.

In Table 3, it is seen that 5th grade students develop 20 different metaphors about the concept of democracy. Accordingly, the metaphors developed by the students are mostly in the categories of "democracy as a tool of equality" (f: 14), "democracy as a symbol of freedom" (f: 13) and "democracy as a system factor" (f: 6). The most developed metaphors of the students are "justice" (f: 10), "freedom" (f: 9), "independence" (f: 4) and "equality" (f: 4), respectively. Grade 5 students have never developed a metaphor with the categories "democracy as a changing factor according to the perspective", "democracy as a developing and maturing entity" and "democracy as a factor of power".

Table 3: The distribution of metaphors
 of 5th grade students on the concept of democracy into categories

Categories	Metaphors	f	%
Democracy as a tool of peace	Affection (1), Respect (1)	2	4,1
Democracy as a valuable and guiding entity	Honesty (1), Guide (1), Advice(1)	3	6,2
Democracy as a changing factor according to the perspective	-	-	-
Democracy as a tool of equality	Justice (10), Equality (4)	14	29,1
Democracy as a structure of diversity	Election (2), Türkiye (1), The Nation (1) Public (1)	5	10,4
Democracy as a developing and maturing entity	-	-	-
Democracy as a factor of power	-	-	-
Democracy as a symbol of freedom	Freedom (9), Independence (4)	13	27
Democracy as a system factor	Solidarity (3), Modernization (1), Brain (1), Unity (1)	6	12,5
Democracy as a necessity or requirement	Life (3), Education (1), Game Rule (1)	5	10,4
Total		48	100

Table 4: Distribution of metaphors developed by secondary school
 6th grade students on the concept of democracy into categories

Categories	Metaphors	f	%
Democracy as a tool of peace	Peace (5), Order (1)	6	18,1
Democracy as a valuable and guiding entity	Mother (1), Father (1)	2	6
Democracy as a changing factor according to the perspective	-	-	-
Democracy as a tool of equality	Equality (3), Scales (3), Justice (2)	8	24,2
Democracy as a structure of diversity	Marriage (2), Family (1)	3	9
Democracy as a developing and maturing entity	-	-	-
Democracy as a factor of power	-	-	-
Democracy as a symbol of freedom	Freedom (9), Freedom of Thought (1), Sky (1)	11	33,3
Democracy as a system factor	Politics (2)	2	6
Democracy as a necessity or requirement	Heart (1)	1	3
Total		33	100

In Table 4, it is seen that 6th grade students develop 14 different metaphors about the concept of democracy. Accordingly, the metaphors developed by the students are mostly in the categories of "democracy as a symbol of freedom" (f: 11), "democracy as a means of equality" (f: 8) and "democracy as a means of peace" (f: 6). The most developed metaphors of the students are "freedom" (f: 9), "peace" (f: 5), "equality" (f: 3) and "scales" (f: 3). It is observed that 6th grade students do not develop any metaphors with the categories of "democracy as a changing factor according to the perspective", "democracy as a developing and maturing entity" and "democracy as an element of power".

Table 5: The distribution of metaphors of 7th grade students on the concept of "democracy" into categories

Categories	Metaphors	f	%
Democracy as a tool of peace	Happiness (1)	1	2,7
Democracy as a valuable and guiding entity	Ataturk (1)	1	2,7
Democracy as a changing factor according to the perspective	-	-	-
Democracy as a tool of equality	Justice (8), Equality (2)	10	27,7
Democracy as a structure of diversity	Election (4), Family (1)	5	13,8
Democracy as a developing and maturing entity	Flower (1), Life (1)	2	5,5
Democracy as a factor of power	Difficulty (1)	1	2,7
Democracy as a symbol of freedom	Freedom (7), Freedom of Thought (1)	8	22,2
Democracy as a system factor	Politics (1), Republic (1), Human (1)	3	8,3
Democracy as a necessity or requirement	Need (2), Life (2), Heart (1)	5	13,8
Total		36	100

Table 5, it is seen that 7th grade students develop 17 different metaphors about the concept of democracy. Accordingly, the metaphors developed by the students are "democracy as a tool of equality" (f: 11), "democracy as a symbol of freedom" (f: 8), "democracy as a structure of diversity" (f: 5) and "necessity". or democracy as a necessity or requirement" (f: 5). The most developed metaphors of the students are "justice" (f: 8), "freedom" (f: 7) and "election" (f: 4), respectively. "Democracy as a tool of peace", "Democracy as a valuable and guiding entity", "Democracy as a changing factor according to the perspective" and "Democracy as a factor of power" are the categories in which 7th grade students develop the least metaphor.

Table 6: The distribution of metaphors of 8th grade students on the concept of "democracy" into categories

Categories	Metaphors	f	%
Democracy as a tool of peace	-	-	-
Democracy as a valuable and guiding entity	-	-	-
Democracy as a changing factor according to the perspective	-	-	-
Democracy as a tool of equality	Equality (2), Scales (1), Rain (1), Justice (1)	5	10,4
Democracy as a structure of diversity	-	-	-
Democracy as a developing and maturing entity	Tree Roots (1), Wood (1), Sycamore (1), Baby (1), Life (1)	5	10,4
Democracy as a factor of power	Sovereignty (2), A Soldier's Ammunition (1)	3	6,2
Democracy as a symbol of freedom	Freedom (15)	15	31,2
Democracy as a system factor	Republic (4), State (2), Brain (2), Country Integrity (2), Politics (2), Mind (1), Human (1), Innovation (1), Form of Management (1)	16	33,3
Democracy as a necessity or requirement	Life (2), Water (1), Habit (1)	4	8,3
Total		48	100

In Table 6, it is seen that 8th grade students develop 24 different metaphors about the concept of democracy. Accordingly, the metaphors developed by students are mostly in the categories of "democracy as a system factor" (f: 16) and "democracy as a symbol of freedom" (f: 15). The most developed metaphors of students are "freedom" (f: 15) and "republic" (f: 4), respectively. It is observed that 8th grade students do not produce any metaphors with the categories of "democracy as a tool of peace", "democracy as a valuable and guiding entity", "democracy as a factor that changes according to the perspective" and "democracy as a structure of diversity".

4. Discussion

In this study, secondary school students developed 53 metaphors for the concept of "democracy". These metaphors are mostly freedom, equality, justice, life, election, republic, peace, politics, independence, scales, solidarity, country integrity and freedom of thought metaphors. When the literature on the concept of democracy is examined, it is seen that similar findings are reached. In the study of Soydaş (2010), students developed the most metaphor about the concept of freedom towards democracy. In the study of Yüce and Demir (2011), police candidates associated the concept of democracy with the concepts of bird, chameleon, human, scales, lion, wolf, water, bee, ant, tree and nature. In the study of Sadık and Sarı (2012), elementary school students perceive democracy as a form of government synonymous with the concepts of equality, freedom and justice; They appear to emphasize democracy as the protector of social order and rights. The concept of democracy in the study of Gömleksiz et al. (2012); It is associated with the concepts of free people, people, family, sea, love and life. In the study of Dündar (2012), primary school students compared democracy mostly to the concepts of rainbow, sun, earth, flower, star, water, nature, life and paradise. In the study of Karatekin and Elvan (2016), they associated the concept of democracy of 8th grade students with the words of equality, freedom and right. In the study of Nasırcı and Sadık (2017), elementary teacher candidates associated the concept of democracy with the concepts of equality, water, air, sun, flower, bird, mother and bread. In the study of Ibret, et al. (2018), pre-service teachers focused on the freedom, sun, seesaw, water, scales, tree, equality, bird, life, justice, father, rainbow, sky, shield, breath, train and conscience metaphors. Accordingly, it is seen that the results of the studies in the literature support the results obtained from this study.

The metaphors developed by the secondary school students were categorized using the study of Yüce and Demir (2011) titled "Examining the perceptions of the police candidates about the concept of democracy through metaphors". Metaphors developed by students are gathered under 9 different conceptual categories. Accordingly, students developed metaphors in the categories of democracy as a tool of democracy and equality as the symbol of freedom. Democracy as a factor of power and democracy as a valuable and guiding entity are the categories in which students develop the least metaphor. When the literature is analyzed, it is seen that in the study of Sadık and Sarı (2012), the metaphors developed by elementary school students on democracy are mostly

concentrated in the category of fundamental rights and freedoms. In the study of Karatekin and Elvan (2016), it was determined that there are 7 different categories related to democracy in the cognitive structures of 8th grade students. These categories are named as human rights, state administration, law, state, value, Atatürk and its principles and citizenship. Students mostly associated the concept of democracy with human rights. In the study of Dündar (2012) examining the democratic perceptions of elementary school students, a dream-like democracy categories existed as a symbol of equality regarding the concept of democracy, which teaches how to live together, and that coexist.

Primary school students have developed a metaphor for the category of democracy that exists with the most rules. In addition, students emphasized that democracy is a regime based on the principle of justice dominated by laws. In the study of Kaldırım (2005), elementary school 8th grade students stated that they were aware of the importance of political and social rights, gender equality and freedom of opinion provided by democracy. In the study conducted by Yüce and Demir (2011) on the study of the perceptions of police candidates on the concept of democracy through metaphors, police candidates developed metaphors in the categories of democracy as the element of democracy and power as the most freedom understanding regarding democracy. Gömleksiz et al. (2012), in the study in which Social Studies teacher candidates examined the metaphors of the concept of democracy, the categories of equality and freedom, sheltering diversity, turmoil and weakness, necessity and inaccessibility were developed. In the study of Yağan Güder and Yıldırım (2014), prospective teachers developed the metaphor for the category of equality and justice most. In the study of Nasırcı and Sadık (2017), the categories of necessity, equality, social order, effort, freedom, personal interests, power, progress, protection and nothingness were developed from the metaphors of the elementary teacher candidates. In the study of Ibret et al. (2018), pre-service teachers perceive the concept of democracy as a changing element, democracy as a tool of equality, democracy as a factor of power, democracy as a system element. In the literature, it is seen that the way participants perceive democracy differs. This can of course be considered as a reflection of the participants' different experiences on democracy. However, it can be said that these results in the literature partially support the results of this study. It is understood from both literature and this study that democracy is perceived as personal liberties and not limiting these liberties, it is necessary for providing equality and justice, is vital and must be in every area of life. However, the fact that secondary school students do not develop any metaphors regarding the category of "democracy as a changing factor according to the perspective" is important in terms of showing that the values and skills such as respect, empathy and cooperation are not sufficiently obtained.

In the study, the metaphors developed by secondary school students towards the concept of democracy were also examined according to the grade level. Accordingly, 5th grade students are justice, freedom, independence and equality; 6th grade students' freedom, peace, equality and scales; 7th grade students justice, freedom and choice; 8th grade students associated metaphors with freedom and republic. The metaphor that

students develop jointly at all grade levels is freedom. Metaphors of 5th grade students are mostly in the category of democracy as a tool of equality; 6th grade students in the category of democracy as a symbol of freedom; 7th grade students have been included in the category of democracy as a tool of equality and 8th grade students in the category of democracy as a system element. When the findings of the study were analyzed at the grade level, students developed the most metaphor related to freedom in the concept of democracy. When the literature is analyzed, Gürbüz (2006) 7th and 8th grade students agree with the expressions about the most freedom concept among the elements of democracy. They determined that it was explained by the words. When the metaphors developed by the secondary school students towards the concept of democracy are examined, it is seen that they emphasize the characteristics of someone to choose, do and act what they want without being hindered or restricted, to ensure that individuals have equal rights in society, to observe and fulfill rights and law, and to ensure the participation of individuals in management.

In this study, the metaphorical perceptions of secondary school students towards the concept of democracy were examined. It was seen that students perceived democracy as a tool of freedom and equality. However, democracy is a phenomenon in all areas of life. For this reason, it may be recommended that practitioners provide democracy training on this issue. In addition, the democratic attitudes and behaviors of the practitioners will contribute to the development of students' perceptions of democracy. Examples can be given in the textbooks of courses on the subject, such as Social Studies, that democracy is a part of every life. They can contribute to democracy education by conducting different studies in qualitative, quantitative and mixed models that will reveal students' views on democracy.

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